

Communal Boundary Conflicts in Nigeria: An Assessment of the 2006 Ebom - Ebijakara Boundary Conflict in Cross River State.

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Abstract

This research is primarily centered on Communal Boundary Conflicts, specifically, the 2006 Ebom – Ebijakara Boundary Conflict in Cross River State, Nigeria. The study examines the negative impact of internal boundary conflicts on the people of Abi Local Government Area, and the State. The objective of the research is to highlight the impact of internal boundary conflicts on the two communities in Abi Local Government Area and Cross River State, drawing the attention of the State policymakers and researchers to the “neglect” of the communal boundary issues involving the peoples under consideration. The historical methodology adopted for this research involved the use of both primary and secondary sources. Field survey and personal interviews used for the analysis of the paper constitute the primary sources. The secondary sources include published and unpublished works on the vexed issues of the State’s internal boundary conflict. The paper adopt the grass root theoretical approach and Collins Model theory of conflicts analysis, and by way of conclusion submits that, internal boundary conflicts between the two farming communities in Abi Local Government Area of Cross River State have been inundated by incessant boundary conflicts which in turn led to the destruction of properties and loss of lives. The affected communities have been denied development arising from insecurity. It recommends that both State and Local Government Areas as well as non-state actors should adopt an imaginative policy option that would lead to peaceful settlement of the conflicts and attainment of peace, progress and security not only in the conflict affected communities but also in the entire Local Government Area and the State at large.

Key words: Boundary Conflict; Communal Conflicts in Abi Local Government, Cross River State.

Résumé

Cette recherche porte principalement sur les conflits frontaliers communaux, en particulier le conflit frontalier entre Ebom et Ebijakara en 2006 dans l'État de Cross River au Nigéria. L'étude examine l'impact négatif des conflits frontaliers internes sur les habitants du Département d'Abi et sur l'État en général. L'objectif de la recherche est de mettre en évidence l'impact des conflits frontaliers internes sur les deux communautés dans le Département d'Abi et de l'État de Cross River, attirant l'attention des décideurs politiques et des chercheurs sur la «négligence» comme élément nourrissant des problèmes communaux. La méthodologie à la base historique adoptée pour cette recherche impliquait l'utilisation de sources primaires et secondaires. Les enquêtes sur le terrain et les entretiens personnels utilisés pour l'analyse du document constituent les sources primaires. Les sources secondaires comprennent des travaux publiés et non publiés sur les questions controversées du conflit frontalier internes de l'État. Comme approche théorique, l'article adopte la théorie

des conflits selon Collins et conclut que les conflits frontaliers internes entre les deux communautés agricoles dans le Département d'Abi de l'État de Cross River ont été modérés par des conflits frontaliers incessants qui a conduit à la destruction des biens et à la perte de vies. Les communautés affectées ont été privées de développement découlant de l'insécurité. L'article recommande que les États et les Départements ainsi que les acteurs non étatiques doivent adopter une politique imaginative qui permette au règlement pacifique des conflits et à la réalisation de la paix, du progrès et de la sécurité non seulement dans les communautés touchées par le conflit, mais aussi dans les autres Départements dans l'État.

Mots-clés: Conflit frontalier; Conflits communaux dans le Département d'Abi, État de Cross River.

Introduction

In Nigeria today, there is strong evidence everywhere that, most of her component states are currently confronted with legions of violence, conflicts and wars that threaten local, state and national integration. A scenario that reflect essentially lack of national integration, political stability and well defined boundaries. This problem has over the years affected the level of socio, political and economic development in the country. Infact, to some scholars of developmental studies, the absence of national integration is the major problem that confronts the developmental efforts of most states in Nigeria (Egbe 38). According to M. Weiner, one of the “central problems of developing nations of Africa that is often more pressing than economic development is the achievement of national integration” (52). Cross River State is not let off the hook as indeed, a variety of conflicts characterise her intergroup relations.

It is evident that incessant outbreaks of communal boundary conflicts in Cross River State are pervasive in all the eighteen Local Governments Areas of the State. For instance, Ugep – Mkpani 1987, Ugep – Idomi 1992, Ugep–Adim 1996 in Yakurr and Biase local government’s areas. Others are between Ikot Ey oNdem, Ikot Ana and Ufut 2005, Ebom and Ebijakara 2006, Ediba and Usumutong 2006, Okuni and Akam 2006 in Akpabuyo, Biase, Abi and Ikom Local Government Areas respectfully, to mention some. However, evidence again shows that resurgence of these boundary conflicts in the State and Nigeria constitute one of the greatest challenges to local, state and national security and developmental aspirations. They also constitutes serious threat to the internal security of Cross River state by adversely affecting one of the most peaceful states of the country, turning her into “a theatre of communal boundary conflicts” (Unigal) and “a state at war with herself” (Akinyele19).

Commenting on the factors responsible for the alarming rate of boundary conflicts in Nigeria generally, Okechukwulbeanu argues that, communal boundary conflicts in Nigeria do not just occur in isolation but begin with “...disputes between two communities fighting over portions of ancestral land” (167-222). While to Ikpe boundary conflicts occur in all the component states of Nigeria resulting in “loss of lives and property” (106). It sometimes lead to total displacement of the weaker communities by the mighty, strong or powerful ones from their homes or farmlands, without immediate plans by either the states government or any of the Non-governmental organizations (NGO) to assist the victims of the conflict by resettling them. A typical example of this scenario is the Ebijakara

community which has since been completely displaced by the Ebom community in 2006 boundary conflict without adequate effort made to help resettle the displaced persons of Ebijakara to date.

This hydra headed monster called communal boundary conflicts “induces fear, insecurity, distrust and economic dislocation” (Ikpe106) whenever it occurs or appears in any of the farming communities of the state. It ends up “creating large stream of Internally Displaced Persons” (IDPS) (106). Thus, this paper examines critically the 2006 Ebom - Ebijakara communal boundary conflict in Abi Local Government Area of Central Cross River State, using the grass root theory of boundary conflict analysis against the state centric theory which connotes separation, division, and restriction of movement at the boundaries of communities, states or nation states (Imobighe 17; Bonchuk 104). In other words, the state centric theory according to Bonchuk, Michael locate boundaries in relations to states and their conflictual postures (24). While the grass root theory of boundary and Collins Model theory of conflict which this paper also hinged on emphasizes “contact and link rather than separation and division as the ultimate function of boundary” (Imobighe 17-18). The theory further emphasized cooperation, mutual and common development of shared resources in the border areas or zones for the mutual benefit of the border dwellers. It locates boundaries as “bridges” across communities not as “barriers”, “integrated” not “separated zones”, as point of contact to be crossed at will especially on those aspect that touches the borders lives such as attending marriages, divinity consultation, various festivals and exchange of ideas and trade (Bonchuk 104). The Collins Model’s theory of conflict according to Ogene, Olukoya believes that, “human beings are sociable but conflict – prone animals” (95). It emphasized that in all human societies, there are differential distributions of human and natural resources which usually lead to a continuous competition between and among groups for greater share of available resources (95). That each community pursues its own interest and naturally, these interests are inherently antagonistic (Collins 60-64). Applying these theories to the study area, it’s observed carefully that, the Ebom – Ebijakara boundary conflict was primarily caused as a result of the two farming communities “fighting over ownership of the ancestral farm land located at their borders.

This 2006 episode of the boundary conflict is however to this day given serious attention or discussed because, it present the “bloodiest conflict turned hostility ever recorded in the history of the two co-habiting communities” (2006 Judicial Committee’s Report). The conflict gradually led to a total displacement and mass exodus of the Ebijakara people away from their ancestral homeland, finding refuge in their neighbouring communities of Yakurr and Obubura Local Government Areas. This is because, the entire community of Ebijakara was completely razed down by the Ebom people and up till this day, no attempt has been made by the Cross River State Government to resettle them (Ebijakara) in their ancestral home. The study seeks to examine the causes of the conflict by drawing the attention of the Cross River State Government and the non – governmental agencies in the state to the antecedents that could be found useful in analysing a boundary conflict of this nature, especially between a people (Arbitration Committee’s Report Vol. 1) “whose economy according to Etiowo, Mbang and Ukpenetu, Eteng is basically governed by the scarce resource of farmland for survival” (Viii; V; 21).

In central Cross River State wherein Abi Local Government Area that harbours

Ebom and Ebijakara communities is located, “land hunger, limited availability of land, overpopulation and pressure on the land” (Goshit60) are always the driving forces that push the people in that region of the state to fight their neighbours beginning with first making “claims to portions of their ancestral land” (Ibeanu 167-222). This is because, land amongst the people according to Best, Idyorough and Shehu is “held as a symbol of prestige” (104 – 106) which every family or indigenes of the communities must possess. This also explains why communal boundary conflicts in central Cross River region will ever continue to be inevitable and dispensable. That whenever there is an attempt by any of the communities in the sub region of the state to either “increase, monopolize or consolidate a particular group’s control over scarce resources such as farmland, fishing waters or trade routes and lately oil rich wells” (Olukoya96) boundary conflict becomes unavoidable. This again however shows that “the people are basically farmers and practically every household a farming unit with hunting and fishing serving as part time occupations that supplement their farming. In other words, agriculture is the main stay of their occupation” (Etiowo Viii; UkpenetuV).

In all, land amongst the people in Africa generally is indispensable as stated by C.H. Enloe that, “every individual, household or community must possess an identifiable homeland for survival” (85) and to R.T., Akinyele “since the issue of survival is closely tied to land ownership, the subject of where the boundary line is drawn has always become very important” (20). This also affirms what scholars like Lord Curzon had earlier said in 1907, that boundary:

Is the razor’s edge on which hung suspended the modern issues of war and peace, of life and death to nations, since the protection of the home is the most vital care of the private citizen, so is the integrity of borders a condition for the existence of modern states (226).

Historical Background of Ebom and Ebijakara Communities

Geographically, Ebom and Ebijakara are two communities amongst others located in Abi Local Government Area of Central Cross River State. They belong to the *Bahumono* group of people, one of the three groups that constitute Abi Local Government Area. Other groups however are the *Agbo and Igbo*. These three groups formed the word “Abi” the name for the people’s Local Government with A for *Agbo*, B for *Bahumono* and I for the *Igbo* people. The groups also speak different languages with the *Bahumono* people speaking “*Kohumono*, the *Agbo* and *Igbo* people speak *Lagbo*” (Stella Osim, interviewed 27/03/2014). Significantly, the *kohumono* and *Lagbo* for the *Agbo* languages or dialect “are of the Bantu linguistic family”. Accordingly, the word “Bantu” means “the people”. It is also a “linguistic classification of a group of closely related languages spoken in the linguistic boundary known as the Bantu line, which runs from the south-eastern area of Nigeria, through Central and Eastern Africa to Southern Africa (Okoi-Uyouyo4).

Other communities that constitute the three different groups in Abi Local Government Area in central Cross River are Itigidi, (the headquarters of the local government), “Igbo Imabana, Igbo Ekwureku, Usumutong, Ediba, Afafanyi, Adadama, Anong, Abeugo, Bazohure and Igonigoni” (Stella Osim interviewed 27/03/2014). These communities are all located North-West of Calabar with about “one hundred and forty four kilometres” (144km)(Urom3) “away from Calabar, the state capital (Ukpenetu iv). North and

south of Abi is the “Ikwo and Afikpo” people in Ebonyi state, east is the Ugep and Ekori in Yakurr Local Government while southeast is the Abayong people in Biase Local Government Areas of Cross River State (Urom4). Though, there are little variations or differences in their languages, they all have a common historical origin.

Historically, the origin of Ebom or the *Bhazokpo* and Ebijakara or Aberiba people of the *Bahumono* group in Abi Local Government Area is first traced to the “Benue Valley”, a general place of origin for people especially within the Central Cross River Region. From Benue valley, Uniga comment by corroborating that the *Bahumono* people “migrated from there to the Cross River Basin” (Uniga24). Uniga further argues that “they were a small group of the *Bakpa* people who first settled at the middle course of the Cross River and later migrated to settle at the hill side of the river, a place called *Othumusa* presently located in between the two communities of Usumutong and Afafanyi” (id.).

To other *Buhumono* people, “*Othumusa* (old town) is their original home of settlement”. According to Nkanu, Sunday Egu “*Othumusa* is an uninhabited piece of land situated further in land. It occupies a central place where communities like Usumutong, Afafanyi and Igonigoni settled around it” (8). He further states that the land till today “serves as an important farm land for all the *Bahumono* communities”. Apart from these versions that have gained wide currency amongst the people, Sunday Ukam, another historian further traced the origin of the Ebom, Ebijakara and the entire (*Bahumono*) people to a place further north called *Akpa*, from where it is believed they later migrated to *Othumusa* (Ukam8).

In History of Nigeria, Elizabeth Isichei traced the origin of the *Bahumono* people to the East, where the people of Eastern Nigeria including the *Ekoi* and the *Bahumono* people in Cross River State were part of the great Bantu dispersal in the 15th and 16th centuries (Nkanu9). David Northrup concurs Elizabeth Isichei’s comment by arguing that, “though the identity of the *Akpa* people with the *Bahumono* people inclusive is not entirely clear, it appears that, the *Bahumono* people were part of the general population movements from the East of Cross River into the area and are possibly identified as an off shot of the *Agwaaguna*” (Northrup 9). In addition to all these versions, E. J. Alagoa argues that the people of “*Bahumono*” of South – Eastern region of Nigeria, are part of the *Ekoi* people thought to have descended from the “*Bantus*” and that the *Bahumono* people have a common origin with the Yakurr, Mbembe, Assiga, and the Agbo. He further insists that this group of people also formed the third migratory group to leave the Cameroons many centuries ago (Nkanu10).

Origin of the Conflict

Prior to the outbreak of the 2006 communal boundary conflict between the Ebom and Ebijakara communities of the *Bahumunu* group in Abi Local Government Area of Cross River State, there had been earlier boundary conflicts occurring between these two communities. Typical amongst earlier conflict was the “1911 incident” which later led to Supreme Court Judgments of 1962 and 1964” (Judicial Commission’s Draft Report 12) respectively. The 1911 conflict and the subsequent Supreme Court Judgment of (1962 and 1964) made provisions for the creation of clearly defined boundaries between the two communities, which by implication suggested that, prior to 1911 and the subsequent 1962

and 1964 Supreme Court Judgments on the case, there were practically no clear cut boundaries between the two communities. Rather what could be said to be inexistence or practiced by the people in pre-colonial period was the “Traditional Land Lease System” (Arbitration Committee’s Report on Ugep -Idomi Land Dispute 28), which only allowed members from both communities to farm on the “Idle” land known as “*Rehot ObaziInah*” (Judicial Commission’s Draft Report 8). The troubled land in question was declared a buffer zone after the 1964 Supreme Court Judgment in order to maintain peace between the people.

But, toward the later stage of their peaceful co-existence, precisely from 2000 to 2006 they began again to “experience deep seated animosity, mutual suspicion and hatred occasioned by the same land ownership tussle” (Judicial Commission’s Draft Report 8). This is because the State Government of Cross River could not implement the Supreme Court Judgment of 1962 and 1964 with the Ebijakara people becoming scared “over the increasing population of the Ebom community and the pressure the population will exert on the land” (Uniga52).

Geographically, from the Judiciary Drafts Report of the Commission set up by the State Government, the land in question is located in between the two communities of Ebom and Ebijakara. It stretch towards Igonigoni, a neighbouring community to both communities and terminates at the Cross River Beach located west of Ediba and Itigidi, the headquarters of Abi Local Government Area (Judiciary Commission’s Draft Report 9).

Causes of the Boundary Conflict

Quite a number of factors contributed to the outbreak of the hostility between Ebom and Ebijakara communities in Abi Local Government Area in 2006. Amongst the many factors are:

Immediate Causes:

The only immediate cause of the hostility or boundary conflict between the two communities was the “incident of 10th January 2006, where a couple of youths from Ebom community were alleged to have recklessly beaten up one Mr.Nkanu Osim Ikongho of Ebijakara community” (Judiciary Committee’s Draft Report 6). The beating up of Mr.Nkanu Osim Ikongho was however traced to a minor disagreement between the youths of both communities (Judiciary Commission’s Draft Report 6). From the evidence adduced by the Ebijakara community in the Commission’s Report “the attack on Mr.Nkanu Osim Ikongho infuriated the youths of Ebijakara who in retaliation, launched an attack on the Ebom community on the 11th of January, 2006” (Judiciary Commission’s Report 6). However, what followed after was a reprisal attack by the Ebom community which was aided by the use of explosives and other sophisticated weapons (Judiciary Commission’s Draft Report 6).

Remote Causes:

- (i) Lingering land tussle since over ownership of the virgin land, traditionally called “*Rehot Ina Abasi*” or “*Rehotobaziina*” by both communities since 1911 (Judicial Commission’s Draft Report 9).
- (ii) Unguarded utterances by members of both communities laying strong claims to land ownership of the area which further fan the existing members of both communities

into disunity (Judicial Commission Draft Report 10).

(iii) Political marginalization spanning from the struggle on who fills the only seat allotted to the two communities at the local government council politics (Uniga, 16; Judicial Commission's Draft Report 10). Accordingly, "Ebom is two-third the size of Ebijakara community with seven villages while Ebijakara is just a single village and one-third of the Ebom community but both shear one council ward seat (Uniga 53). Filling the only slot meant for them at the local government council is always a serious contest as the seven villages in Ebom always want to be represented before considering the Ebijakara community" (Uniga 53), that since the inception of Abi Local Government in Cross River, "all except one of the Councillors from Ebijakara had represented the Ebom-Ebijakara Council Ward, as a result, the Ebijakara people always feel marginalized and aggrieved" (Judiciary Commission's Draft Report 11).

(iv) "Existing deep-seated animosity, mutual suspicion, distrust and hatred as a result of claims and counter claims of land ownership" (Judiciary Commissions' Draft Report 8).

(v) "Administrative or bureaucratic bottleneck". From the Draft Report of the (Judiciary Commission of Inquiry, 12), it is revealed that, the "delay and non-implementation of Government decisions" also contributed to the immediate outbreak of the hostility between the two communities in 2006. That is "between 1911 and 1964 when the Supreme Court Judgment on the land ownership claims between Ebom and Ebijakara communities was last delivered, there had also been series of decisions reached by the Court at various levels" (Judiciary Commission's Draft Report 12) including the WACA agreement, but "without any follow-up action to permanently create the required established boundary or demarcate the disputed land for which judgment had been delivered already" (Judiciary Commission's Draft Report 12). The last Supreme Court Judgment of 1964 which had bearing on the disputed land had been left unexecuted until the outbreak of the violence again in January 2006 (Judiciary Commission's Report 12).

Impact Assessment of the Conflict:

The impact of the conflict on both communities cannot be taken lightly because; it led to loss of lives, property and total displacement of the Ebijakara community. "Though Ebom suffered a death toll of thirty four persons, their reprisal attack on the Ebijakara people was much more devastating as it recorded a total of one hundred and thirty four (134) casualties between 11th and 15th of January, 2006. Some of the casualties were declared missing till date" (Judiciary Commission's Draft Report 14-15).

Secondly, the two communities lost their property. "A total of one hundred and ninety five persons across five wards of Ebom community lost their property in that dispute. These wards are *Abego, Anoikpata, Fanavcu, Egbezum* and *Bawetiti* while in Ebijakara", the destruction was total as the entire community particularly the "Old Town" was razed down completely including schools and church buildings" (Judicial Commission's Drafts Report 16).

Concerning the economic aspect, Uniga maintained that, both communities suffered a lot of hardship as the people could not access their farms to get supplies either for consumption or distribution for money (Uniga 58), as every activity between them ceased and the beaches that were of economic importance could not be utilized to earn revenue (58).

Demographically, the death toll from both communities, either as displaced persons or those who wilfully left the community to settle outside because of insecurity in the area, has brought about depletion in the population size of the two communities (Uniga 59).

Politically, the conflict affected the two communities especially the Ebijakara people as “they were cut off from their political friends” (Oka 78). “During electioneering campaigns, politicians from other Bahumono communities, the state and national could not go to Ebijakara and Ebom communities for campaign for fear of either being killed or molested” (78;Uniga 58). This resulted in the two communities being politically alienated from the local government council and other parts of the state and country’s elections held at that time (Oka 78; Uniga 58).

More latently, the conflict disrupted the educational system through the involvement of students in the conflict which retarded prospective progress (Oka 78). While their counterpart in other communities, Local Government and the State were intensifying their studies through extra-mural lessons, in Ebom and Ebijakara for instance, the basic school program was destabilized as it affected adversely, the chances of that generation of finalist to gain admission into any of the Nigerian Universities (78).

Weapons Used In Fighting the Conflict

Paragraphs 3.2.7, page 24 of the (Judicial Commission Drafts Report) on the hostility between Ebom and Ebijakara communities in Abi Local Government Area, both communities of Ebom and Ebijakara depended so much on “fetish means for aggressive and defensive purposes through the application of latent forces, to wit, oracles, juju and other barbaric and uncivilized disposition” (Judicial Commission’s Draft Report 13). The report further maintained that, for the two communities to sustain the potency of these forces, there had to be over indulgence in ritual killings and sacrifices to such oracles and shrines in the areas, a development which had led to numerous reported cases of sudden and mysterious disappearance of persons from within and outside their neighbouring communities (Judicial Commission’s Draft Report 13).These latent forces used by both communities were imported from the neighbouring African countries such as Ivory Coast, Benin Republic and the Cameroun where some of the indigenes from the two communities reside (Judicial Commission’s Report 13).

Recommendations and Conclusion

Conclusively, it could be said that it is no longer news, that the main cause of the conflict between Ebom and Ebijakara communities as presented in the paper was the issue of farmland ownership which has over the years presented the two communities as an area where land related conflicts are to be expected always and unavoidably.

The following recommendations on the way forward are made based on the

data/information from sources such as interviews, journal articles, memoranda, books and Judicial Commission's Draft Report.

(i) That either the State Government or the Boundary Commission should clearly define the boundary line between the two communities in order to clearly show where each community end as a panacea for lasting peace (Judicial Commission's Report).

(ii) That the Area Command or Zone Six of the Nigeria Police should create a Police Post in every community that is not up to having a Police Station in order to help arrest culprits and prevent the escalation of such crises as recommended in the Report of the Arbitration Committee on the Ugep-Idomi Land Dispute 1992.

Finally, the authors also recommends that, the state government of Cross River should "speedily" and urgently put in place the appropriate modalities for early resettlement of the Ebijakara community through the provision of security and enabling environment for the people" (Judiciary Commission's Draft Report 22.

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Name of Interviewees	Age	Occupation	Place of Interview	Date of Interview
OvatRajunor	56 Years	Business Man	Calabar	16/02/2013
Stella Osim	52 Years	Lecturer	Calabar	27/03/2014
NkanuRekpene	61 Years	Business Man	Calabar	18/02/2013